

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th June 2022

Accepted: 01st July 2022

Online: 22nd July 2022

KEY WORDS

pancreatic juice, gastric juice, proteolytic activity, casein-fat emulsion, fat hydrolysis products, casein, tributyrin, sunflower oil.

INFLUENCE OF FATS AND THEIR HYDROLYSIS PRODUCTS ON THE PROTEOLYTIC ACTIVITY OF THE PANCREAS AND GASTRIC JUICES

Djalalova Ozoda Kasimjanovna

Andijan State Medical Institute , Andijan, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6880544>

ABSTRACT

The effect of different concentrations of fat and fat hydrolysis products on the proteolytic activity of the pancreas and gastric juice was studied using casein-fat emulsion (casein+tributyrin, casein+sunflower oil). Under the influence of sunflower oil hydrolysis products, the total proteolytic activity of pancreatic juice clearly decreased, but this indicator did not change under the influence of tributyrin hydrolysis products. Hydrolysis products of sunflower oil and tributyrin oil do not affect the total proteolytic activity in gastric acid environment. We saw a decrease in the proteolytic activity of the pancreas when the concentration of the above-mentioned fats was increased in the composition of the casein + fat emulsion. Increasing the concentration of fats affects the proteolytic activity of gastric juice.

A number of studies have shown the important role that physiological surfactants play in the digestion of proteins. These studies did not take into account the effect of certain gastrointestinal enzymes on protein digestion characteristics. For example, lipases of the stomach and pancreas can certainly play an important role in modifying the structure of the emulsion through the formation of surface-active free fatty acids and mono- and diglycerides from oil-phase triglycerides [3, 5] .

Casein has been shown to bind both oleic acid and taurocholic acid. Thus, the presence of undigested protein in the upper part of the small intestine can interfere with the absorption of lipids by the mucous membrane by a double action,

including direct binding of fatty acids to protein and impaired micellar solubilization of lipids due to binding of bile acids [7, 2] .

There is an explanation that lipids bind to the secondary binding site of bovine β -lactoglobulin fatty acids, thereby blocking the action of proteases for steric reasons. These data show how biomolecular interactions between proteins and lipids can change proteolysis patterns and should be considered in any digestion model. [4]

Due to the competitive adsorption of proteins and desorption by lipase proteins from the surface of fat droplets, many proteins adsorbed on the surface of fat droplets can interfere with the hydrolysis of fats by pancreatic

lipase. Moreover, the adsorption of proteins on the surface of fat droplets can affect their hydrolysis by proteases. In addition, interactions with fatty acids can also affect their hydrolysis by proteases.

Objective: to study the effect of the interaction of casein with fats and fatty acids on the proteolytic activity of pancreatic and gastric juice.

Material and methods. The work used gastric and pancreatic juices obtained in chronic experiments in dogs with fasting secretion. In the first of the second series we studied the effect of different concentrations of fat hydrolysis products TPA [1] under the influence of pancreatic and gastric juice using casein-fat emulsion (casein+ tributyrin, casein + sunflower oil). In conditions of use as a substrate with gastric or pancreatic juice: casein only (0.5%), water-in-oil emulsion (1.0%) without pre-incubation, without casein with pancreas, water-in-oil emulsion (1.0%) after a preliminary 30 minutes pre-incubating it without casein with pancreatic juice, water-in-oil emulsion (1.0%) after a preliminary 60 min. pre-incubating it without casein with pancreatic juice.

In the second series, the effect of various concentrations of fats on TPA [1] was studied under the influence of pancreas and gastric juice using casein-fat emulsion (casein + tributyrin, casein + sunflower oil). In conditions of use as a substrate with gastric or pancreatic juice: casein only (0.5%), 1.0% oil emulsion, 1.5% oil emulsion, 2.0% oil emulsion.

Statistical processing was carried out by the method of variation statistics with the calculation of average values and their average errors, determination of the reliability coefficient of the Student-Fisher difference (t). The differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ or less.

Results. As a result of studies of the first series, which studied the effect of different concentrations of fat hydrolysis products on the pancreatic and gastric juice. It was found that the TPA values of pancreatic juice when using emulsion of casein and sunflower oil as a substrate, without preliminary incubation of oil with pancreatic juice, were significantly higher compared with the indicators of TPA of pancreatic juice using only casein as a substrate. At the same time, the indicators of TPA of pancreatic juice when using emulsion from casein and sunflower oil, after a preliminary 30 minutes the pre-incubation of casein-free sunflower oil with pancreatic juice was significantly, but not significantly, reduced compared to TPA without a fat emulsion using casein only. The same tendency to change the TPA when using emulsion from casein and sunflower oil after a preliminary 60 minutes pre-incubation of sunflower oil without casein from pancreatic juice, which marked a camping even more pronounced significant decline in TPA compared with TPA without fat emulsion. In general, there was a marked gradual decrease in pancreatic juice TPA with an increase in sunflower oil hydrolysis products (Fig. 1 A).

In the study of gastric juice TPA using protein-fat emulsions, it was found. That when using emulsion from casein and sunflower oil, the indicators of TPA when consuming sunflower oil without first incubating it, without casein with pancreatic juice were also significantly higher compared to TPA without fat emulsion. At the same time, TPA indicators when using sunflower oil after a preliminary 30 min. incubations of it without casein with pancreatic juice were also slightly higher compared to TPA without a fat emulsion, but lower than TPA when using sunflower oil without first incubating it, without casein with pancreatic juice. In the obtained research results when using sunflower oil after a preliminary 60 minutes incubating it

without casein with pancreatic juice. Slightly lower levels of TPA were noted compared with those without fat emulsion. As a result, there was a slight decrease in TPA under the influence of gastric juice with increasing concentration hydrolysis products of sunflower oil (Fig. 1B).

When studying the TPA of gastric juice using protein-fatty emulsions from casein and tributyrin, the TPA when using tributyrin had the same dynamics of change, but at a slightly lower level, both without pre-incubation without casein with pancreatic juice, and after a preliminary 30 min. incubation of tributyrin without casein with pancreatic juice, as well as with the use of tributyrin after a preliminary 60 min.

incubating it without casein with pancreatic juice. At the same time, a slightly pronounced decrease in TPA was observed under the influence of gastric juice with an increase in the concentration of products of hydrolysis of tributyrin (Fig. 1 B).

Fig. 1. Change in proteolytic activity under the influence of pancreatic (A) and gastric (B) juice using casein-fat emulsion. In conditions of use as a substrate with gastric or pancreatic juice: 1 - casein only, 2 - oil emulsion without preliminary re-incubation of it without casein with pancreatic juice, 3 - oil emulsion after a preliminary 30 min. pre-incubating it without casein with pancreatic juice. 4 - oil emulsion after a preliminary 60 minutes pre-incubating it without casein with pancreatic juice.

* - significantly different values with respect to indicators of using only casein as a substrate with gastric or pancreatic juice.

tributyrin after a preliminary 30 min. without its casein incubation with pancreatic juice was and is not significantly higher indicators TPA without the fat emulsion, but below the TPA, when used uu tributyrin without preincubation it without casein with pancreatic juice. The same tendency to change the TPA was observed with the use of tributyrin after a preliminary 60 minutes. incubating it without casein with pancreatic juice. In general, the observed negligible e reduction TPA under the influence of pancreatic juice with increase of concentration of products of hydrolysis of tributyrin (Fig. 1 A).

Discussion of the results. The results of studies where studied the influence of

different concentrations of fat hydrolysis products TPA influenced pancreatic juice, using, as a vegetable oil or tributyrin, composed of casein and fat emulsion. They showed a significantly pronounced increase in TPA under the influence of pancreatic juice. With an increase in the hydrolysis products of both sunflower oil and tributyrin, a decrease in TPA was observed, more pronounced with the use of sunflower oil. At the same time, the data obtained, which studied the effect of various concentrations of fat hydrolysis products on TPA under the influence of gastric juice, using sunflower oil or tributyrin in the casein-fat emulsion, revealed a significant significant increase in TPA.

With an increase in the concentration of hydrolysis products of sunflower oil or tributyrin under the influence of gastric juice, an increase in TPA was noted, which was less pronounced compared with the indicators of TPA under the influence of pancreatic juice. These results showed that in an alkaline environment, with an increase in the products of hydrolysis of sunflower oil, a marked decrease in TPA under the influence of pancreatic juice can be associated with the possibility of the formation of fatty acids, the concentration of which increases with increasing time of incubation of sunflower oil. The resulting fatty acids when interacting with casein molecules have the ability to create complexes that can inhibit the action of pancreatic juice proteases. At the same time, in an acidic environment, with an increase in the products of hydrolysis of sunflower oil, a less pronounced decrease in TPA is observed under the influence of gastric juice. This may be due to the fact that the formed fatty acids, the

concentration of which increases with increasing pre-incubation time of sunflower oil, may have a less pronounced ability to form complexes with casein molecules in an acidic environment.

Also, the results of the studies showed that when using protein-fat emulsions using tributyrin and casein, a less pronounced decrease in TPA was observed under the influence of both pancreatic and gastric juice with an increase in the concentration of tributyrin hydrolysis products. This may be due to the fact that the formed fatty acids, the concentration of which increases with increasing pre-incubation time of sunflower oil, may have a less pronounced ability to form complexes with casein molecules in an acidic environment.

The obtained results of these studies are additional confirmation that the difference in the physicochemical structure of these oils affects the difference in effects when using the products of hydrolysis of sunflower oil and tributyrin. This may be due to the fact that the formed fatty acids, the concentration of which increases with increasing pre-incubation time of tributyrin, may have a less pronounced ability to form complexes with casein molecules, which could promote the action of pancreatic juice proteases in an alkaline environment, and could also contribute in an acidic environment to the action of pepsin of gastric juice. At the same time, the difference in effects when using the hydrolysis products of sunflower oil and tributyrin is affected by the pH of the medium. In an acidic environment, the strength of the interaction of casein with fatty acids of both sunflower oil and tributyrin is lower. This may be due to the fact that in an acidic environment, fatty acids of both sunflower oil and

tributyrin may have less pronounced ability to form complexes with casein molecules that could inhibit the action of gastric juice pepsin in an acidic environment.

As a result of studies in the study of the effect of different concentrations of sunflower oil in the composition of the protein-fat emulsion on TPA under the influence of pancreatic juice, it was found that a pronounced gradual increase in TPA under the influence of pancreatic juice with an increase in the concentration of sunflower oil was established. This is due to the fact that proteins have adsorption, as well as ordered deployment on the surface of fat droplets, which contributes to their more accessible pepsinolysis [3]. The results can also be explained by the fact that with an increase in the concentration of sunflower oil in the composition of protein-fat emulsions, the number of fat drops and the total surface of these drops increase. Due to this, the amount of casein adsorbed on fat droplets increases, and this interaction improves the effect of proteases on casein molecules, as a result, there is an increase in the TPA of pancreatic juice and gastric juice when using protein-fat emulsion.

Conclusions: Thus, it can be concluded that the hydrolysis products of sunflower oil and tributyrin by pancreatic lipase contribute to a decrease in pancreatic juice TPA, with less pronounced effects of tributyrin hydrolysis products. The hydrolysis products of both sunflower oil and tributyrin in the composition of fat emulsions with casein to a lesser extent affect in the acidic environment a decrease in the gastric juice TPA. An increase in the concentration of sunflower oil in the

emulsion with casein contributes to a significant increase in pancreatic juice TPA. An increase in the concentration of tributyrin in the emulsion with casein also contributes to a significant increase in the pancreatic juice TPA, but this effect is more pronounced than when using sunflower oil.

An increase in the concentration of both tributyrin and sunflower oil in the emulsion with casein has a lesser effect in the acidic environment on the gastric juice TPA, compared to the pancreatic juice in the alkaline environment.

References:

1. Andreeva Yu. V. Effect of fasting and resumption of feeding on the secretory function of the stomach / Diss. ,, Cand. Biol. Science, St. Petersburg, 2007, 140 p.
2. Golding, M., Wooster, TJ, Day, L., Xu, M., Lundin, L., Keogh, J., & Clifton, P. Impact of gastric structuring on the lipolysis of emulsified lipids // Soft matter. - 2011. -the V . 7. - No. 7. - P . 3513-3523.
3. Macierzanka, A., Sancho, AI, Mills, EC, Rigby, NM, & Mackie, AR Emulsification alters simulated gastrointestinal proteolysis of β - casein and β - lactoglobulin // Soft Matter. - 2009. - the V . 5. - No. 3. - P . 538-550.
4. Mandalari, G., Mackie, AM, Rigby, NM, Wickham, MS, & Mills, EC Physiological phosphatidylcholine protects bovine β - lactoglobulin from simulated gastrointestinal proteolysis // Molecular nutrition & food research. - 2009. - the V . 53. - No. S1. - P . S131-S139.
5. Sarkar A., Goh KKT, Singh H. Properties of oil-in-water emulsions stabilized by β - lactoglobulin in simulated gastric fluid as influenced by ionic strength and presence of mucin // Food Hydrocolloids. - 2010. - the V . 24. - No. 5. - P . 534-541.
6. Sarkar, A., Goh, KK, Singh, RP, & Singh, H. Behavior of an oil-in-water emulsion stabilized by β - lactoglobulin in an in vitro gastric model // Food Hydrocolloids. - 2009. - the V . 23. - No. 6. - P . 1563-1569.
7. Sklan D., Budowski P., Hurwitz S. Absorption of oleic and taurocholic acids from the intestine of the chick. Interactions and interference by proteins // Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) -Lipids and Lipid Metabolism. - 1979. - the V . 573. - No. 1. - P . 31-39.
8. Smith, F., Pan, X., Bellido, V., Toole, GA, Gates, FK, Wickham, MS, Mills, EC (2015). Digestibility of gluten proteins is reduced by baking and enhanced by starch digestion // Molecular nutrition & food research. - 2015. - the V . 59. - No. 10. - P . 2034-2043.